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Critical issues for the ground control of shallow roadways in weak ground: a case study

Shuqi Ma¹, Xiaoying Liu^{2,3*}, Marte Gutierrez⁴

¹ Key Laboratory of Transportation Tunnel Engineering, Ministry of Education, School of Civil Engineering, Southwest Jiaotong University, Chengdu, 610031, China

² Institute of Applied Materials (IAM-CMS), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Strasse am Forum 7, 76131 Karlsruhe, Germany

³School of Materials Science and Engineering, Shandong University, Jinan 250061, PR, China

⁴ Civil and Environmental Engineering, Colorado School of Mines, Golden, CO 80401

Abstract:

The roadways located in weak ground experiences strong and cyclic dynamic loading induced by the thick coal seam extraction, which caused costly support and delay of normal production. This paper discusses the critical issues and support strategy for such roadways through a case study on a roof collapsed roadway which was excavated in a coal stratum at a depth of 120 m in Shanxi Province, China. A 2 m high void between the concrete support and the exposed roof strata was left untreated due to the poor roadway construction. The roadway collapse reached up to approximately 6 m in the roof strata, which was attributed to the large untreated void as well as the highly fractured rock mass. A combination support method of the void filling, the fracture grouting and rock bolting was proposed to rebuild and reinforce the roadway. The deformation of the roadway was effectively controlled and the maximum roof displacement reached 135 mm. The failure mechanism of the roadway was numerically investigated by the discontinuous deformation analysis (DDA) based on the specific geological conditions. The numerical findings suggested that the void above the roadway could significantly impact on the stability of overlying strata.

Keywords: discontinuous deformation analysis (DDA); roadway collapse; void effect; void filling; fracture grouting.

Introduction

Underground tunnels and mining roadways are usually constructed in rock mass with joints, faults, and weak zones (Wu et al. 2004; Ma et al. 2017a, 2017b). Many factors could impact on the stability of the underground constructions. These factors vary from the construction quality to the

* Corresponding author

Email: xiaoying.liu@kit.edu

inherent characteristics of the rock mass (Yeung and Leong, 1997). Many failures of underground excavations are associated with rock joints. Jaeger and Cook (1979) stated that rock joints sets are sometimes parallel and regularly spaced and sometimes these rock joint sets are in different inclinations. Rock mass is divided into separate blocks by these rock joints. The joints have low shear resistance and tensile strength. Rock blocks around the underground openings may slide along the rock joint or detach from the rock mass, leading to the collapse of the roadway. The general used methods to reinforce the jointed rock mass include grouting and rockbolting (Ma et al. 2014a; Nemcik et al. 2014; Ma et al. 2016a, 2016b; Zhao et al. 2018).

Numerous roadways have been excavated in underground coal mines in China. Roof strata stability is a major concern during the roadway construction due to the poor construction quality and unfavorable geological conditions. Roadway collapse could occur even in a shallow depth. Zhongcun Coal Mine which is located in Jincheng City, in Shanxi Province China, encountered a severe roof collapse in a roadway at a depth of approximately 120 m. The drill and blast method was used during the roadway excavation. The surrounding rock mass of the roadway was significantly disturbed by the drill and blasting excavation. A large void with the height of 2 m was left between the concrete support and the exposed roof strata because of the poor roadway construction. The roof collapse reached up to as far as 6 m. The catastrophic collapse severely damaged the roadway and led to temporary close of the mine.

This paper will present a case study on the roadway collapse, with the focus on the support design and collapse analysis. Studies have been carried out on support design and deformation monitoring for roadway or tunnels (Sharma et al. 2001; Basarir 2006; Genis et al. 2007; Gurocak et al. 2007; Sopacı and Akgün 2008; Rasouli 2009; Li et al. 2013; Ma 2014). However, their methods deal with the small collapse of the tunnels, i.e. 1-2 m or even smaller collapse of the roof strata. While in the case of Zhongcun Mine, the roof collapse reached 6 m. Hence, the methods presented in the above studies could not be simply applied herein.

Better understanding of the failure mechanism of the roadway collapse is highly required and also important for future support design and roadway excavations. Physical modelling, analytical and numerical approaches have been used to investigate the collapse mechanism of the roadway (Everling 1964; Hatzor and Benary 1998; Jia and Tang 2008; Li et al. 2013; Senent and Jimenez 2015; Huang et al. (2017)). Everling (1964) studied the performances of rock joint deformation using a model test. Goodman et al. (1972) carried out a scaled model test to investigate the roadway deformation in jointed rock mass. Jeon et al. (2004) studied the effects of fault and grouting on the roadway stability using scaled model tests. Huang et al. (2017) proposed an analytical solution to predict the collapse of a roadway which is excavated above a karst cave. Physical modelling is time-consuming and it is difficult to represent the realistic situation using a physical model. Analytical solution is usually proposed for a specific situation and additionally, it cannot explicitly take into account the effects of rock joint properties. Numerical modelling provides a useful tool to simulate the real situation in practice.

In numerical analysis, discrete element method (DEM) has been developed to analyze the stability of jointed rock masses around underground openings, e.g. Universal Distinct Element Code (UDEC) (Cundall, 1980), Discontinuous Deformation Analysis (DDA) (Shi 1988) and RFPA (Tang, 1997). DEM is able to capture large displacements of individual blocks, opening of rock joints, rotations and complete detachments of blocks (Jing 1998).

Lee et al. (2003) carried out a parametric study using 2 and 3-dimensional DEM analysis. They pointed out that horizontal joints coupled with vertically dipping joints is the most critical joints set most unfavorable for roof strata stability. Additionally, Lee et al. (2003) showed that the displacement of a key roof block increases with the decreasing block size. Hao and Azzam (2005) numerically examined the effects of fault on the stability of roadways by Universal Distinct Element Code (UDEC). Jiang et al. (2006) analyzed the relationship between the opening deformation and fractal dimension and orientation of joint sets. Jia and Tang (2008) investigated the effects of rock joint inclination angle and the lateral pressure coefficient on the deformation of roadways using the numerical code RFPA. They found that the joint inclination angle and the lateral pressure coefficient significantly affect the stability of roadway.

Yeung and Leong (1997) carried out a parametric study using the two-dimensional DDA to investigate the influences of the rock joints on the stability of a roadway. Hatzor and Benary (1998) studied the stability of a horizontally bedded and vertically jointed roof (referred to as a laminated Voussoir beam) in an underground water storage reservoir using the discontinuous deformation analysis (DDA). Their study found that the stability of a laminated voussoir beam is controlled by the interplay between joint spacing and the joint friction angle. Tsearsky and Hatzor (2006) carried out a study on roadway roof deflection in blocky rock masses using DDA with the focus on the effects of joint spacing and friction. They found that the joint spacing rather than the joint shear strength plays a major role in the extent of the roof loosening zone above the opening. Hatzor et al. (2010) studied the limiting relationship between the span of underground excavation and its cover height for stability in jointed rock masses using DDA. Park (2001) investigated the mechanical responses of inclined jointed rock mass during roadway construction based on a physical trap door model. Wu et al. (2004) numerically modelled these experiments using DDA and their study indicated that the numerical model could closely represent the physical testing results. Wu et al. (2004) pointed out that the stress arch formed in the roof strata was associated with the joint inclination angle. He and Zhang (2015) numerically investigated arching mechanism for underground excavations in laminated rock masses. They found that a global pressure arch and a group of local arches were formed. The weight of the overlying strata is transferred to the abutments via the global pressure arch. Zhang et al. (2016) carried out 3D geo-mechanical model tests to analyze the deformation of an underground cavern. Afterwards, they numerically modelled the whole process of the physical tests using the nodal-based Discontinuous Deformation Analysis (NDDA). DDA is used in this study to numerically model the effects of rock joints on the stability of roadway as it has the capability to explicitly represent the joint properties and to properly model the rotation of the falling blocks.

Grouting material plays an important role in reinforcing the geomaterials. There has been a variety types of materials which are developed to improve the stability of pavement, tunnels and roadways (Cetin, 2013a; Chen et al. 2017; Ma and Chen 2017; Altera et al. 2019). For example, researchers have proposed to mix recycled low-density polyethylene (LDPE) material with other materials to create porous plastic pavement (Brooks and Cetin 2012, 2013; Cetin et al. 2012a, 2012b; Cetin 2013b, 2015a, 2015b). For coal mine underground roadways, grouting materials which can set up fast are usually required in order to provide quick support to the roadway (Chen et al. 2012; Ma et al. 2014b). In the case study presented herein, a fast setting grouting material was used with the aim to maintain the roadway stability.

The objective of this study is to provide insights into the collapse mechanism for the roadway,

which would be very helpful for tunnel or roadway construction under similar geological conditions. The background of the roadway collapse was first introduced. The collapse mechanism of the roadway was numerically investigated based on the specific geological conditions. A combination support method of the void filling, the fracture grouting and rock bolting was proposed to reinforce the roadway. The novelty of this study lies in the fact that it employs the discontinuous deformation analysis (DDA) to explore the collapse mechanism of roadways excavated in jointed rock mass. The adopted DDA method could closely represent the behavior of rock joints and yield good prediction on the overall behavior of rock mass.

Critical issues for the ground control of shallow roadway in weak ground

This section will present the critical issues causing the collapse of the shallow roadway in weak ground. Zhongcun Coal Mine is located in Jincheng City, in Shanxi Province, China. Fig. 1 shows the geological column chart. The tunnel was excavated in the coal seam. Sandy mudstone was the immediate roof strata of the tunnel. Table 1 shows the mechanical properties of these rock strata, which were obtained from laboratory tests on the cylindrical rock cores of boreholes. The overlying strata above the tunnel (mudstone and sandy mudstone) are weak strata. These weak strata were further fractured due to the weak ground condition. It means that the surrounding rock mass is very unstable after the roadway excavation.

Fig. 1 The geological column chart.

Table 1 Mechanical parameters of rock strata.

A roadway at a depth of approximately 120 m was excavated in the coal seam using the drill and blast method. Due to weak ground condition, the blasting operation resulted in a larger cross-section than that planned. The surrounding rock masses were subjected to a high degree of disturbance and were highly fractured after excavation. Fig. 2a schematically shows the constructed roadway before roof collapse. The original support method of the roadway was concrete shell and rockbolts. A large void with the maximum height of 2 m was left between the concrete arch and the roof strata of the roadway. A mine employee was able to stand on the concrete arch prior to the roof collapse. The end-anchored rockbolts failed to provide effective reinforcement to the highly fractured and loosened roof strata (Ma et al. 2017c, 2017d; Ma et al. 2018a, 2018b). The roof collapse occurred after the concrete construction work. The fragments of the roof rock mass fell on the floor. Fig. 3 shows the photos of the collapsed roadway in Zhongcun Mine. Timber support was used to prevent further collapse of the roof. The cross-section of the roadway after the roof collapse is schematically shown in Fig. 2b. Roof fall reached approximately 6 m high in the overlying strata.

Fig. 2 Schematic illustration of failure of the underground roadway. (a) before collapse; (b) after collapse.

Fig. 3 Photos of the collapsed roadway. (a,b), the roadway after collapse; (c,d) timber support to prevent further strata failure.

Based on the field investigation, this catastrophic roof collapse was believed to be associated with three factors: (1) the concrete arch did not provide any supports to the highly fractured roof strata due to the large void between concrete arch and the roof strata; (2) the surrounding weak rock mass was severely disturbed or fractured by the excavation process; (3) the installed rockbolts did not provide reinforcement functions to the surrounding rock mass. The failure mechanism of the shallow roadway in weak ground is numerically studied using DDA.

Numerically investigation of the failure mechanism by DDA

DDA is a discontinuum based numerical method, which is specifically designed to model the behavior of jointed rock masses. The DDA software is programmed in the C++ programming language. In the DDA method, the domain concerned is treated as an assemblage of second-order discrete blocks. Fractures in DDA are explicitly represented and the individual blocks interact via mutual contacts. The failure mechanism of the roadway of Zhongcun Mine was investigated using DDA. The focus of this numerical study will be on the effects of the void presence and the joint orientation angles on the roadway stability.

The 2D-DDA model of the roadway is shown in Fig. 4. The close-up view of the area of interest is shown in Fig. 4b. The model was built based on the geological information given in Fig. 1. Different colors are used to represent different rock layers in Fig. 4. Rock strata 1 and 7 were discretized into large blocks, as they were a bit far away from the roadway and had little effects on the numerical outcomes. Rock strata 2-5 were discretized into smaller blocks with the average size of $0.9\text{ m} \times 1.8\text{ m}$.

The objective of the numerical analysis is to investigate the effects of the void and joint inclination angle on the roadway stability. It was difficult to detect the joint conditions inside the roof strata. According to the field observation on the exposed rock mass, two possible rock joint groups were assumed herein. In rock joint group 1 as shown in Fig. 4, one rock joint set had an inclination angle of 60° to the horizontal bedding joint whereas the other joint set was inclined at 150° to the horizontal bedding joint. In rock joint group 2 as shown in Fig. 5, one rock joint set had an inclination angle of 45° to the horizontal joint while the other was inclined at 135° .

Field statistics shows that the average size of the fallen blocks is $0.3\text{ m} \times 0.6\text{ m}$ (length \times width). Hence, the area of interest was discretized into smaller blocks with the size of $0.3\text{ m} \times 0.6\text{ m}$, as shown in Figs. 4b and 5, in order to closely represent the actual roof collapse.

Fig. 4 The 2D-DDA model of the roadway. (a) The overall roadway model; (b) the close-up view of the area of interest.

Fig. 5 The joint group 2 used in the numerical analysis.

Numerical model parameters

The block properties used in the simulation are shown in Table 2. These values were obtained from the mechanical parameters of rock strata as listed in Table 1. The following DDA control parameters were used in the DDA model: the penalty stiffness is $5e8$ N/m; the shear spring stiffness is $2e8$ N/m; maximum step time increment is 0.0001. The displacement allowed ratio, which controls the allowable displacement for each block within each computing step, was first set to 0.0005. After 30000 steps of the simulation by when the blocks in the DDA model were stabilized, the displacement allowed ratio was adjusted to 0.07 to enable the DDA model to simulate large deformation after the roadway excavation. The dynamic parameter used in this study was 0.999.

Table 2 DDA block properties used in the roadway model.

The joint parameters for rock strata 1-7 are shown in Table 3. The parameters of the intact rock strata (friction angle, cohesion and tensile strength) given in Table 1 were adopted for the joint properties used in this numerical model. This enabled the assemblage of blocks to represent the mechanical behaviors of the intact rock. The properties of rock joints within the area of interest marked by the dashed rectangles as shown in Fig. 4b are also shown in Table 3. Smaller values were used for the joint properties, as the strata within these areas were highly fractured due to the excavation disturbance.

Table 3 Rock joint properties used in the DDA model.

Vertical and horizontal stresses

Environmental stresses play a key role in the stability of underground structures and hence, their values must be carefully and accurately defined in the numerical model. The vertical stress applied on the upper boundary of the DDA model is 2.5 MPa, which is calculated by:

$$\sigma_v = \rho \cdot g \cdot h = 2.5 \text{ MPa} \quad (1)$$

where the averaged density $\rho = 2500 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and $g = 10 \text{ m/s}^2$ were used.

Kang et al. (2009) and (2016) carried out detailed studies on the in-situ stress distributions in the underground coal mines located in Shanxi Province. According to Kang et al. (2016), the vertical stresses at the depth of 101 m and 122 m were 2.53 MPa and 3.05 MPa, respectively. Hence, the calculated vertical stress of 2.5 MPa at the depth of 100 m was accurate for the Zhongcun Mine in Shanxi Province.

Kang et al. (2009) carried out measurements on in-situ stresses at coal mines in Shanxi Province and gave the distribution of the ratio of the mean horizontal principal stress to the vertical principal stress. They found that the ratio ranging from 0.5 to 1.0 accounted for 53.75% for underground

mines in Shanxi Province. Accordingly, the ratio of the mean horizontal principal stress to the vertical principal stress was chosen as 0.7 in this DDA modelling, i.e. the applied horizontal stress $\sigma_h = 1.75$ MPa.

Variables in the numerical study

Four models as given in Table 4 were carried out in this study and the variables were joint inclination angles and the void status. These models were run for 40000 steps to reach the initial stress equilibrium and afterwards, the roadway was excavated. All the models were run for a total of 150000 steps. Analysis of each model took around 7 hours. For Models 1 and 3, the rock mass within the void area was excavated at the same time as the roadway excavation whereas the rock mass within the void area in Models 2 and 4 was not excavated.

Table 4 Four models in the numerical analysis

The vertical stress of the point M1 (see Fig. 4a) was recorded in the four models and Fig. 6 shows the vertical stress history of the four models. Fig. 6 also includes the analytically computed value (-3 MPa) at the point M1. As can be seen, the four models reached the initial ground stress after 11000 steps. The four models match well with analytical solution in terms of the initial stresses. The measurements in Models 1 and 3 show that the vertical stress at M1 dropped from -3 MPa to 0 at 40000 step due to the excavation of rock masses in the roadway area and in the void area. In comparison, the vertical stresses in Models 2 and 4 decreased and remained at around -2.4 MPa after the roadway excavation.

Fig. 6 Vertical stress vs the DDA step for four models.

Results of Models 1 and 2

Fig. 7a shows the results of Model 1 at step of 150000, in which the rock mass within the void area were excavated. It can be seen that the roof collapse reached up to a height of about 6 m, which was close to the in-situ condition. The results of Model 2 at step of 150000 are shown in Fig. 7b for comparison. As can be seen, the roadway in Model 2 was not damaged by the roadway excavation and the roof strata remained stable. The difference between Models 1 and 2 was that the void in Model 2 was still filled with the fractured rock mass. It can be seen that the DDA model is able to simulate the roof collapse of the underground roadway; and the void could significantly impact on the stability of the roadway.

Fig. 7 Results at step of 150000. (a) Model 1; (b) Model 2.

When the roadway was excavated, the initial stress equilibrium was disturbed and the stresses within the rock mass around the opening were redistributed. The jointed rock mass in the roof would become loosened and fall until a pressure arch was formed. Figs. 8 and 9 show the

evolutions of the principle stress distributions around the roadways in Models 1 and 2, respectively. It can be seen from Fig. 9 that a pressure arch was developed immediately around the roadway in Model 2 after the roadway excavation. The concrete shell and the un-excavated void played a key role in the formation of the pressure arch, which transferred the weight of the overlying strata to the two abutments of the arch and protected the stability of the roof strata above the roadway.

However, the artificial concrete shell in Model 1 did not contribute to the stabilization of the roadway. The roof strata became loosened up to a height of about 6 m, due to the large void above the concrete shell. A large amount of loosened rock blocks fell to the floor. In the end, a pressure arch which was far away from the roadway was formed in the roof strata. The rock blocks above the pressure arch are stable.

Fig. 8 Evolution of the principle stress distribution in Model 1.

Fig. 9 Evolution of the principle stress distribution in Model 2.

Results of Models 3 and 4

Fig. 10 shows the results of Models 3 and 4. As can be seen, the roof strata collapsed 3.6 m high in Model 3 where the rock mass within the void was excavated. The roadway in Model 4 showed good stability as the void was filled with the fractured rock mass.

Fig. 10 Results at step of 150000. (a) Model 3; (b) Model 4.

Fig. 11 shows the stress evolution around the roadway in Model 3. It can be seen that much less rock blocks collapsed in the roadway of Model 3 than that of Model 1, which was attributed to the different rock joint sets used in the two models. It can be seen from Fig. 11 that the rock joint group 2 (rock joint inclination of 45° and 135°) led to quicker formation of the pressure arch than joint group 1 (rock joint inclination of 60° and 150°). The angle between the major principle stress (the vertical stress in this case) and the joint plane could affect the roadway stability. Rock mass tend to be more stable with the increase of the angle between the vertical stress and the joint plane (The angle between the vertical stress and the joint plane in Model 3 is larger than that of Model 1). It can be seen from Fig. 11 that the formed pressure arch prevented the further collapse of the jointed rock mass above the arch and hence the roadway in Model 3 saw less amount of falling blocks.

It can be seen from Fig. 12 that the pressure arch was formed around the concrete shell in Model 4 after the roadway excavation. The existing rock mass in the void area helped form pressure arch preventing the collapse of overlying rock mass, which was the same as in Model 2.

Fig. 11 Evolution of the principle stress distribution in Model 3.

Fig. 12 Evolution of the principle stress distribution in Model 4.

The support design of the roadway

Due to the large void and the development of the fractures in the rock mass, the concrete shell did not provide any support to the exposed rock mass and hence, the highly fractured mudstone and sandy mudstone fell on the floor. A support method was proposed to repair this roadway and to reinforce the overlying rock mass. Based on the field observations and the numerical analysis, the support method should be able to reduce the effects of the voids and fractures, i.e. it should include void filling and rock joint grouting. The proposed support method is summarized as follows.

a) A temporary support

First of all, a temporary support as shown in Fig. 13 was designed to protect workers from potential rock falls when rebuilding the concrete shell. Under the temporary support, the workers rebuilt the shell wall using the concrete blocks and cement mortar. The rebuilt concrete shell is shown in Fig. 13 as well.

Fig. 13. The concrete shell constructed under the protection of the temporary support.

b) Void filling

After the concrete shell was rebuilt, the large void between the concrete support and the exposed rock mass needs to be filled. A fast setting material was used to fill the void. This material consists of two types of powders, which can be mixed together with water to generate a solid material with high compressive strength in a short time (approximately 15-20 minutes). This material has been widely used in underground coal mines in China (Chen et al. 2012). Uniaxial test was carried out on the material with the water-solid ratio of 1.5:1. The obtained stress-strain curve is shown in Fig. 14 (Zhang et al. 2015). The filling plan is schematically shown in Fig. 15a. The materials must be mixed properly and afterwards, the mixture was pumped into the void.

Fig. 14 The experimentally obtained stress-strain curve of the material.

Fig. 15 Filling the void between the concrete shell and the exposed rock mass after collapse.

c) Rock mass grouting

After the void was filled, the highly fractured rock mass was reinforced by pumping the fast curing material into rock mass. Three boreholes were drilled in the roof strata after the filling work. The grouting plan is shown in Fig. 15b.

d) Rockbolts and cables

In the end, 20 mm diameter, 2.4 m long rock bolts and 17.8 mm diameter, 8 m long cable bolts were used to reinforce the roof strata above the roadway. The bolt support pattern is shown in Fig. 16.

Fig. 16 Roof bolt pattern. (a), Cross-sectional view; (b), Top view. Unit, mm.

Field measurements on the deformation of surrounding rock mass were carried out. Fig. 17 shows the measurements of roof-floor convergence and the rib-rib convergence. The roof-floor displacement reached approximately 135 mm in the first 23 days after roadway construction. From that day onwards, the surrounding rock mass of this roadway remained stable, indicating that the proposed support method was able to control the stability of the underground roadway.

Fig. 17 The measurement results of roadway

Discussion and Conclusions

This paper presents a case study on a large roof collapse of a roadway which was excavated in a coal stratum at a depth of 120 m in Shanxi Province, China. The roadway was excavated using the drill and blast method. Due to weak ground conditions, the excavation resulted in a large cross section of the roadway and highly fractured rock mass in the overlying rock strata. A large void with the height of 2 m between the concrete support and the roof strata was left untreated due to the poor roadway construction. The overlying strata collapsed after the roadway construction and the roof collapse reached up to about 6 m. The collapse was mainly attributed to the large void and the highly fractured rock mass. A support method was proposed to rebuild and reinforce the roadway. The large void between the concrete shell and the exposed roof strata was filled by the mixture of two powders. The fractured rock mass was later reinforced by grouting. After that, bolts and cables were installed to reinforce the overlying roof strata. The measurement showed that the maximum roof displacement was 135 mm, indicating that the applied support method effectively minimized the movements of surrounding strata and improved the stability of roof strata.

This paper made an attempt to investigate the failure mechanism of the roof strata using discontinuous deformation analysis (DDA). The numerical study reveals that the void in the overlying roof strata of roadway could pose significant safety concerns in the roadway excavation. Two rock joint groups were used in the DDA model. It was found that the DDA model has the capability to simulate the large roof collapse of the roadway. The roof collapse occurred in Models 1 and 3 where the roadway and rock masses in the void area were excavated. Model 1 with the

rock joint group 1 (rock joint inclination of 60° and 150°) was able to closely simulate the in-situ roof collapse, whereas Model 3 with the rock joint group 2 (rock joint inclination of 45° and 135°) showed less roof collapse. The difference is related to the different rock joint inclination angles, as other parameters such as stress boundary conditions, block properties, rock joint properties and the block sizes are the same for Models 1 and 3. The larger the angle between the joint plane and the major principle stress, the more stable the roadway becomes.

In Models 2 and 4 where the rock mass within void area was not excavated, the roof strata remained stable. This indicated that the void significantly impacted on the roof stability. The rock mass within the void could help quickly form the pressure arch, which transfer the weight of overlying strata to the two abutments of the arch and improve the stability of the roof strata above the roadway. Hence, special attention must be paid to minimize the void in the roof strata in the field. This also reflected that the used reinforcement method (the void filling and the fracture grouting) could effectively improve the stability of the roadway.

Based on these findings, other roadways in Zhongcun Coal Mine and roadways in Duanshi Coal Mine (these two mines belong to Qinhe Energy Group Company Ltd.) were carefully examined and the detected voids were filled by the fast setting material. These reinforced roadways remained stable after the repair work.

Although this study is based upon the semicircle tunnel, the findings can be applied to tunnels with other profiles such as rectangular tunnels and horse-shoe tunnels. The uncertainties in this study involve the unknown geological information of the inclination angle of joints, the distribution of joints within rock mass, the strength of joints, the size and profile of voids, etc. Hence, careful investigation on these geological information should be conducted prior to the practical application. The numerical method provides an useful tool to analyze the mechanism of tunnel collapse, and to aid the reinforcement design of tunnels in the field. However, this has to be combined with the experienced engineers in order to ensure both safety and cost-effectiveness of the reinforcement method.

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1 **Figure Captions**

2 Fig. 1 The geological column chart.

3 Fig. 2 Schematic illustration of failure of the underground roadway. (a) before collapse; (b) after
4 collapse.

5 Fig. 3 Photos of the collapsed roadway. (a,b), the roadway after collapse; (c,d) timber support to
6 prevent further strata failure.

7 Fig. 4 The 2D-DDA model of the roadway. (a) The overall roadway model; (b) the close-up view
8 of the area of interest.

9 Fig. 5 The joint group 2 used in the numerical analysis.

10 Fig. 6 Vertical stress vs the DDA step for four models.

11 Fig. 7 Results at step of 150000. (a) Model 1; (b) Model 2.

12 Fig. 8 Evolution of the principle stress distribution in Model 1.

13 Fig. 9 Evolution of the principle stress distribution in Model 2.

14 Fig. 10 Results at step of 150000. (a) Model 3; (b) Model 4.

15 Fig. 11 Evolution of the principle stress distribution in Model 3.

16 Fig. 12 Evolution of the principle stress distribution in Model 4.

17 Fig. 13 The concrete shell constructed under the protection of the temporary support.

18 Fig. 14 The experimentally obtained stress-strain curve of the material.

19 Fig. 15 Filling the void between the concrete shell and the exposed rock mass after collapse.

20 Fig. 16 Roof bolt pattern. (a), Cross-sectional view; (b), Top view. Unit, mm.

21 Fig. 17 The measurement results of roadway

22

23 **Table Captions:**

24 Table 1 Mechanical parameters of rock strata.

25 Table 2 DDA block properties used in the roadway model.

26 Table 3 Rock joint properties used in the DDA model.

27 Table 4 Four models in the numerical analysis

28

Thickness: unit, m	Rock strata	Depth: unit, m
9.2	Sandstone	109.2
2	Mudstone	112.2
6.2	Sandy mudstone	118.4
1.81	Mudstone	120.21
3.9	Sandy mudstone	124.11
3.3	Coal seam	127.41
2	Mudstone	129.41
8	Sandstone	137.41

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Fig. 17 The measurement results of roadway

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Table 1 Mechanical parameters of rock strata.

Rock strata	Young's Modulus, GPa	Density, kg/m ³	Poisson	Friction angle, degree,	Cohesion, MPa	Tensile strength, MPa
Sandstone	28.3	2680	0.19	36	20	2.54
Mudstone	12	2500	0.26	25	8	0.63
Sandy mudstone	23.2	2560	0.2	30	13	1.38
Coal seam	5	1400	0.3	20	3	0.2

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Table 2 DDA block properties used in the roadway model.

Rock strata	Young's Modulus, GPa	Density, kg/m ³	Poisson's ratio
Sandstone, for strata 1 and 8	28.3	2680	0.19
Mudstone, for strata 2, 4, and 7	12	2500	0.26
Sandy mudstone, for strata 3 and 5	23.2	2560	0.2

Coal seam, for strata 6	5	1400	0.3
Concrete shell	35	2500	0.25

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Table 3 Rock joint properties used in the DDA model.

Rock joint within various strata	Friction degree, °	angle,	Cohesion, MPa	Tensile strength, MPa
Sandstone, for strata 1 and 8	36		20	2.54
Mudstone, for strata 2, 4, and 7	25		8	0.63
Sandy mudstone, for strata 3 and 5	30		13	1.38
Coal seam, for strata 6	20		3	0.2
Concrete shell	38		25	4
Disturbed area in strata 4, 5 and 6, marked by the dashed rectangles in Fig. 4b	13.3		2	0.13

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Table 4 Four models in the numerical analysis

Models	Joint inclination	Void	Block number before excavation	Block number after excavation
Model 1	Joint group 1: rock joint inclination of 60° and 150°	Excavated	1914	1753
Model 2	Joint group 1: rock joint inclination of 60° and 150°	Not excavated	1914	1818
Model 3	Joint group 2: rock joint inclination of 45° and 135°	Excavated	1900	1731
Model 4	Joint group 2: rock joint inclination of 45° and 135°	Not excavated	1900	1804

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